

Current Status of 6 GHz DC Magnetron Sputtering Thick Film Deposition

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INTRODUCTION

At LNL, the R&D on the coating film technology for Niobium on Copper cavities is of great importance since the development of Quarter Wave Resonators of the ALPI accelerator. The 6 GHz elliptical cavities represent a low-cost research that is a key step to go through from the prototypes into the real cavities, in the framework of the accelerator technology.

Thick films deposited in long pulse DCMS deposition mode onto 6 GHz copper cavities have demonstrated the mitigation of the Q-slope at low accelerating fields [1]. The main goal of the deposition of thick films is to reproduce the superconducting properties of the Nb bulk.

In this work, different characterization techniques have been applied to Nb thick films cavities to study the morphology, the response to a DC magnetic field, and RF performances.

COATING TECHNIQUE

For the deposition of the thick films (~45 μ m), the post magnetron configuration has been used (Fig. 1). The source of the magnetic field that will allow the sputtering process to develop, is located outside the vacuum chamber. The cavities are deposited by long pulse DC magnetron sputtering. Single layers of hundreds of nanometers grow consecutively in order to avoid stress in the thick film that might reduce its quality.

Fig. 1. (a) Deposition system by post-magnetron sputtering technique. (b) Design of system. (c) Cavity configuration inside the system.

THICK FILM MORPHOLOGY

Thorough analysis by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) characterizations were made to samples from cut coated 6 GHz cavities at STFC.

The coating technique by long pulse deposition showed a higher grain structure than the one-shot deposition (coating without any pauses in the process). Furthermore, the dispersion of the histograms representing the grain sizes, was also smaller. In the figure 2, it is possible to observe the EBSD characterization for cavity 16 deposited by long pulse mode where each pulse thickness is 500nm (a), and cavity 7 deposited in one pulse mode (one-shot).

Fig. 2. EBSD characterization: (a) Long pulse deposition (cavity 16). (b) One pulse deposition (cavity 7).

SEM characterization showed a dense, without voids, and columnar growth of the Nb thick film onto the Cu cavities. In Fig. 3, it is evident the homogeneity of the morphology when approximately 30 microns of Niobium are deposited in the equator of the cavity.

Fig. 3. SEM characterization of Nb film on Cu cavity.

The characterization also shows a differential grain growth in dependence with the relative angle between the source (Nb target) and the substrate (Cu cavity). The preferential growth affects the critical temperature locally, as reported in [2].

DC MAGNETOMETRY

The DC magnetometer permits a further study of the response of samples under a magnetic field (performed at STFC). Estimations of the superconducting properties is given by the change of the magnetic momentum of the sample respect to the applied magnetic field.

Fig. 4. Magnetization loop of samples cut from cavity.

The magnetization loops shown in Fig. 4, shows the different responses depending on the position of the cavity. From this characterization, it is possible to infer, qualitatively, that there is less magnetic flux trapped in the equator respect to the iris, considering, as well, the different orientation of the crystal growth, due to the relative angle between the substrate and the cathode. This statement is due to the capability to the sample to return to its initial conditions that may be described, as well, comparing the internal areas of the loops. Furthermore, the full penetration field (H_{fp}) and the upper critical field (H_{c2}) can be estimated from the graph [3] to be $H_{fp} \sim 148$ mT and $H_{c2} \sim 330$ mT. While for the Nb bulk $H_{c1} = 180$ mT $H_{c2} = 280$ mT. It is possible to compare with thin films produced during the ARIES collaboration to be $H_{fp} \sim 15$ mT and $H_{c2} \sim 290$ mT. The comparison between these values implies the improvement of the superconducting properties of the thick films of Niobium respect to the thin films that represent the standard in the coated cavities technology. It is important to highlight that the measurements were done on samples cut directly from cavity 21, that presented a Q-slope mitigation (constant performances) at low accelerating fields.

To understand the systematical improvement of the superconducting properties for the thick films, a similar characterization was made to different films. These films were stripped from the cavities 07, 16 and 21 and placed onto Kapton for the estimation of H_{fp} . These three cavities were coated using different parameters and presented different performances during the RF test. However, the three samples presented a similar behavior of H_{fp} being 154

mT, 114 mT, and 148 mT respectively.

COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (CT)

One of the well-known challenges of the reproducibility of the Nb coated cavities is the substrate reproducibility. Defects could prevail in the surface of the copper cavity after the mechanical and chemical treatments applied. These small defects on the substrate surface are reproduced by the film that grows on top. In Fig. 5, it is possible to observe the effect mentioned before by a CT scan.

Fig. 5. Computed tomography on cavity 21 (by STFC).

CONCLUSIONS

Niobium thick films on copper cavities have shown to be an alternative for the thin films, due to their assemblance with the Nb bulk superconducting properties. Large grain columnar structure promotes an efficient field expulsion that may be comparable to Nb bulk values. Even though, the reproducibility continues to be an issue for the coated cavities technology.

FUTURE WORK

The main goal of the 6 GHz prototype cavities is the further scalability of the research to bigger cavities. In the following year, efforts will be focused on the design and construction of a DC post magnetron configuration for 1.3 GHz cavities. The reproduction of the 6 GHz to 1,3 GHz cavities will be done to test the Nb thick films sputtered at high temperature (if possible).

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